
Psychoeducation as an Effort to Increase Understanding of Compliance for LKSA Ar-Royyan Students

Isyatin Rodiyah¹, Yuni Nurhamidah², Robi'atul Adawiyah³

¹Postgraduated Student, University Of Muhammadiyah Malang, Jl. Raya Tlogomas No. 246 Malang-East Java, Indonesia

²Lecture, University Of Muhammadiyah Malang, Jl. Raya Tlogomas No. 246 Malang-East Java, Indonesia

³Postgraduated Student, University Of Muhammadiyah Malang, Jl. Raya Tlogomas No. 246 Malang-East Java, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The different backgrounds of students can be a trigger for disobedience, where obedience is a person's fulfillment of another person's request which is also defined as an action or deed carried out based on the wishes of another person or doing what is ordered by another person. Obedience is also obedient, obedient, submissive, obedient to teachings and rules. Psychoeducation is carried out as an effort to increase students' understanding of obedience. This research aims to determine the effect of providing psychoeducation in increasing student compliance. The subjects in this research were 18 people. This research is a quasi-research with a pre-experimental design method with a pre-test and post-test one group design type. This research shows that there is a significant difference in scores between treatment without psychoeducation and treatment with psychoeducation ($t = -16.663$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). So it can be concluded that psychoeducation can be used to increase students' understanding of obedience.

KEYWORDS: Psychoeducation, Compliance, Students

I. INTRODUCTION

Child development can never be separated from the role of both parents, but not all children are fortunate to be able to experience direct care from both parents for various reasons, such as economic reasons, parents who are no longer there, and conflict between the parents and ultimately the child cannot living together with his parents (Fadhillah, Uyun, & Sulistyarini, 2017). LKSA Ar-Royyan is not much like an orphanage in general, where an orphanage is a place to care for orphaned, orphaned or orphaned children, even children who have been abandoned by their parents with the aim of being nurtured into independent, responsible children, as well as being obedient and useful for society, nation and religion (Putri, Rahmi, & Erita, 2024). The Ar-Royyan Child Welfare Institution (LKSA) was established on May 13 2014 under the auspices of the Ukhuwah Insaniyah Foundation which is located at Jl. Sulfate Canal No. 47 Malang City. This institution was founded with the aim of assisting government programs in overcoming social problems by caring for orphans, orphans and children from underprivileged families. This institution has 21 students, 10 boys and 10 girls with ages ranging from 7-18 years. There are 10 administrators of this institution with an additional 3 male musyriks and 2 female musyriks, the musyriks here act as an extension of the institutional administrators in supervising the students of LKSA Ar-Royyan who are also teachers at Madrasah Diniyah at LKSA Ar-Royyan.

Activities at LKSA Ar-Royyan are systematic with students attending formal schools at institutions that have collaborated with LKSA Ar-Royyan, Madrasah Diniyah activities at LKSA Ar-Royyan itself, and religious activities in the evening which are mandatory activities for all students. With the different backgrounds of each LKSA Ar-Royyan student, this causes several problems to be faced, one of which is non-compliance by the students. Disobedience here is the students' refusal to obey the rules that have been made by LKSA Ar-Royyan. Another problem that was found was that students did not receive systematic care from the management of LKSA Ar-Royyan, the management directly monitored the activities carried out at LKSA Ar-Royyan with the help of 5 musyriks, 3 male musyriks and 2 female musyriks. This creates a lack of a strong sense of bond between the supervisor and the students because the assistance is not specific to each student.

The different backgrounds of students can be a trigger for disobedience, where obedience is a person's fulfillment of another person's request which is also defined as an action or deed carried out based on the wishes of another person or doing what is ordered by another person. Obedience is also obedience, compliance, submission, compliance with teachings and rules (Purwanti & Amin, 2016). Disobedience of students at LKSA Ar-Royyan takes the form of students disobeying the rules that already exist in the institution and ignoring orders from administrators and musyrik, where obedience is a form of behavior that surrenders oneself completely to those who have authority, not based on anger or anger increased aggression, but more in the form of their

Psychoeducation as an Effort to Increase Understanding of Compliance for LKSA Ar-Royyan Students

relationship with parties in authority (Purwanti & Amin, 2016). Because students are under the authority of the institution, they automatically submit themselves to the institution and are obliged to carry out the rules set by the institution.

Obedience is accepting all orders from other people, a person can be said to be obedient to other people if he has three aspects of obedience related to obedient attitudes and behavior. Blass states that aspects of obedience include belief, accept, and act (Blass, 1999; (Wardani & Sari, 2024)). Obedience for most individuals is embedded in behavioral tendencies and stronger encouragement from ethical training, sympathy, and moral behavior which then makes obedience an important thing in life. Milgram mentioned several factors that could cause compliance, namely, legitimacy of authority figures, support from fellow colleagues, location status, closeness of authority figures, and personal responsibility (Milgram, 2009; (Hendrawan & Rahayu, 2021)). A person can be said to be obedient when he believes and accepts that he wants to obey, which is then followed by the act of obeying. Someone will be obedient due to various factors, someone will be obedient to orders because they see that the person giving the order is someone who is very influential in their life.

Based on several of these problems, it is deemed necessary to provide interventions for students to better understand the concept that obedience is important to apply in everyday life. Psychoeducation is an intervention approach that combines psychotherapy and education which is used as a preventive measure, in line with the explanation from HIMPSI that psychoeducation is an effort to prevent psychological disorders from arising and even becoming more widespread in a society, community or group by increasing understanding and even skills society, group or community. Psychoeducation is carried out with the aim of providing useful information and training in improving psychological perceptions along with useful strategies for increasing wellbeing (Pradnyaswari, Suminar, & Marheni, 2022). Therefore, this research aims to provide psychoeducation to students to increase their understanding of obedience.

II. METHOD

This research uses a quantitative research design with a quasi-experimental method. An experimental method that has treatment, impact measurement, experimental units, but does not use random assignment to create comparisons in concluding changes caused by treatment (Sugiyono, 2019). The method used is pre-experimental design with a pre-test and post-test one group design type given to one group without a comparison group. The subjects in this research were 18 LKSA Ar-Royyan students. Data collection in this research used several methods, namely surveys, interviews and observations. The survey was conducted to obtain initial results before the psychoeducation program was carried out, interviews were conducted to explore the results of the survey conducted to obtain qualitative results, then observations were carried out to observe the behavior of LKSA Ar-Royyan students.

The procedures carried out in this research began by exploring the problems that occurred based on the results of interviews and observations, which were then used as the basis for preparing instruments in this research and preparing material to be presented in the psychoeducation process. In the second stage, the researcher prepared a psychoeducational module to be used in this research. The third stage is the process of implementing psychoeducation, in this process there are various sessions starting from introducing and building bonds between researchers and participants, providing pre-tests, providing psychoeducation material which includes the definition, aspects and factors of compliance then material about the importance of being obedient in daily life, after providing the material there is a question and answer process between the participants and the researcher and ends with giving a post-test to the participants. In this research, the researcher acts as a speaker. The fourth stage in this research is overall data analysis of the research results. The data obtained from the pre-test and post-test results will be processed using SPSS for Windows version 25 software. The Paired Sample t Test analysis is used to compare the average scores before and after psychoeducational treatment.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the psychoeducation program that has been implemented, the results show changes between before and after the psychoeducation program, where students are given psychoeducation about the importance of being obedient. This can be seen from the increase in pre-test and post-test scores given to students. The results of the analysis are as follows:

Table 1. Description of Data on Understanding Obedience

Group Statistics					
	Category	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Scoring	Pre Test	18	56.11	10,922	2,574
	Post Test	18	79.44	8,024	1,891

Psychoeducation as an Effort to Increase Understanding of Compliance for LKSA Ar-Royyan Students

The results of the pre-test obtained by students have a quite large difference in the total average score from the post-test, where the results of the pre-test average score are 56.11 while the results of the post-test average score are 79.44. This can be interpreted as meaning that there is a change in students' understanding of the importance of being obedient, after being given material related to obedience. Students said that there was a change in understanding why being obedient was very important to carry out in daily activities and understanding that being obedient was very important because it was in order to maintain moral and social burdens for oneself. The description of the differences in results after providing psychoeducation is as follows:

Picture 1. Pre-test and post-test instruments

Then the scores were analyzed using the Paired Sample t Test to prove the differences between the pre-test and post-test. The analysis test results are as follows:

**Table 2. Descriptive Paired Sample t Test
Pre-test and Post-test data**

N	Average Score		Correlation	T	P
	Pre	Post			
18	56.11	79.44	0.847	-16,663	0,000

The results of this test obtained a correlation of 0.847, this proves that the correlation before and after providing psychoeducation has a real relationship. Meanwhile, in the t value table, the value obtained was -16.663 and the results of the Paired Sample t Test analysis obtained a value of $P < 0.05$ ($P = 0.000$). This shows that there is a significant difference between treatment without psychoeducation and treatment with psychoeducation. So it can be concluded that there is a difference in the scores before and after providing psychoeducation.

The results of the research show that there is an increase in students' understanding of obedience. This is proven by the different score results from the pre-test and post-test where the post-test score results increased after being given psychoeducation. Then these results were strengthened by the results of the Paired Sample t Test analysis which had significant differences before and after providing psychoeducation. Psychoeducation is a program implemented to show an increase in students' understanding of the importance of being obedient in everyday life. This change occurs because of the students' efforts to think and understand the importance of obedience.

In general, psychoeducation is carried out with the aim of providing education and assistance to a person or community so that they can develop sources of support in facing challenges in life. In this research the aim of psychoeducation is to provide additional information or knowledge regarding the importance of compliance. Psychoeducation is an intervention carried out on individuals, families and communities by educating participants regarding significant life challenges, assisting participants in developing sources of support and social support to face these challenges and developing skills in solving them challenge (Griffiths, 2006). In this research, psychoeducation has a positive influence on increasing students' understanding of obedience, thereby making students aware and willing to obey.

There are several theories that form the background of psychoeducation, namely ecological systems theory, cognitive-behavioral theory, learning theory, group practice models, social support models, and narrative approaches (Lukens & McFarlane, 2004). In this research, the theory used is more focused on cognitive theory, where students are given additional knowledge about the importance of obedience in everyday life. So that students have the self-perception that being obedient is very important and

Psychoeducation as an Effort to Increase Understanding of Compliance for LKSA Ar-Royyan Students

beneficial in life because a little free from moral and social burdens, students are able to instill a more disciplined lifestyle in their daily activities.

Psychoeducation can be said to be successful if it meets four things, namely participant reactions, participant learning outcomes, behavior changes, and impact (Supratiknya, 2020).

1. Bad reaction

Shows that participants give positive reactions by willing to take the time to take part in this training activity. Students carefully follow the activities when providing material

2. Participants' learning outcomes

This section assesses the extent to which participants can demonstrate changes in attitudes, increase knowledge, and improve participants' skills. The change that occurs is that students become more understanding that being obedient is very important because it is in order to maintain moral and social burdens for themselves.

3. Changes in behavior

There is a change in the behavior of students who are less likely to violate because they feel that being obedient is much more important and beneficial than breaking existing rules.

4. Impact

With this psychoeducational activity, students better understand the importance of being obedient and willing to obey.

The target of the psychoeducation program can be said to be achieved based on the explanation of these four things. However, there are limitations to this psychoeducation program, namely the lack of additional methods in the psychoeducation process such as discussion and question and answer forums so that it does not provide an active space for participants taking part in activities.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that this case can be overcome with a psychoeducation program. Recommendations for the foundation to be able to provide sustainable programs to overcome students' obedient attitudes, because psychoeducational programs without further programs indicate that students will decline back into individuals who easily break the rules. For future researchers, this research can be developed by developing a psychoeducation program with various additional methods in it.

REFERENCES

- 1) Fadhillah, A. R., Uyun, Q., & Sulistyarini, I. (2017). Pengaruh terapi kognitif perilaku berbasis kekuatan terhadap peningkatan resiliensi pada remaja panti asuhan. *Intervensi Psikologi*, 9(1), 96–107.
- 2) Griffiths, P. (2006). *Introduction to English semantics and pragmatics*. Edinburgh university press.
- 3) Hendrawan, M. M. M., & Rahayu, A. (2021). Konformitas dan Kontrol Diri Perannya Terhadap Kepatuhan Pada Protokol Kesehatan Menjaga Jarak. *Jurnal Psikologi Kreatif Inovatif*, 1(1), 21–29.
- 4) Lukens, E. P., & McFarlane, W. R. (2004). Psychoeducation as evidence-based practice: Considerations for practice, research, and policy. *Brief Treatment & Crisis Intervention*, 4(3).
- 5) Pradnyaswari, A. A. A., Suminar, D. R., & Marheni, A. (2022). Psikoedukasi untuk Meningkatkan Pemahaman Terkait Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus (ABK) pada Guru TK Inklusi 'X' Denpasar. *Psikostudia: Jurnal Psikologi*, 11(3), 479. <https://doi.org/10.30872/psikostudia.v11i3.8318>
- 6) Purwanti, N., & Amin, A. (2016). Kepatuhan Ditinjau Dari Kepribadian Ekstrovert-Introvert. *Jurnal Psikologi*, 3(2), 87–93.
- 7) Putri, S. A. E., Rahmi, A., & Erita, J. (2024). Peran Pengasuh Panti Asuhan dalam Membina Disiplin Diri Anak-Anak Panti Asuhan Muhammadiyah Cab Guguak II. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Ilmu Sosial*, 2(2).
- 8) Sugiyono. (2019). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV.
- 9) Supratiknya, A. (2020). *Merancang Program dan Modul Psikoedukasi*. Yogyakarta: Sanata Dharma University Press.
- 10) Wardani, S., & Sari, K. (2024). Kontrol Diri Dan Kepatuhan Menggunakan Alat Pelindung Diri Petugas Pengangkut Sampah Di Banda Aceh. *Syah Kuala Psychology Journal*, 2(1), 32–45.